

2B: COA Comparison and Evaluation Tool for Avery

Trial	Condition ——	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Condition ——	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Constant Variables	Test Variables	Outcome	Conclusions Next Steps
1	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Repeat
2	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Repeat
3	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Attention is valuable, Evaluate attention and escape
4	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Repeat
5	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Repeat
6	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Attention is valuable, Evaluate tangible
7	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Repeat
8	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Repeat
9	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Compare attention and tangible
10	B	High-preferred Attention	H	Tangible		Attention, Tangible	High-preferred Attention	Repeat
11	B	High-preferred Attention	H	Tangible		Attention, Tangible	High-preferred Attention	Repeat
12	B	High-preferred Attention	H	Tangible		Attention, Tangible	High-preferred Attention	Throughout the assessment, Avery has allocated toward preferred

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								attention, when possible, Evaluate high-preferred RBT to caregiver
13	B	High-preferred Attention	F	High-preferred Attention	Attention	Attention Type (RBT vs. Caregiver)	High-preferred RBT	Repeat
14	B	High-preferred Attention	F	High-preferred Attention	Attention	Attention Type (RBT vs. Caregiver)	High-preferred RBT	Repeat
15	B	High-preferred Attention	F	High-preferred Attention	Attention	Attention Type (RBT vs. Caregiver)	High-preferred RBT	Evaluate responding when high-preferred attention is not available
16	C	Low-preferred Attention	D	Chore Demands		Escape, Attention	No outcome determined	Refuse to make a choice and engaged in challenging behavior, Present new pairings
17	B and D	High-preferred Attention and Academic Demands	C	Low-preferred Attention	Attention	Attention Type, Escape	High-preferred Attention and Academic Demands	Repeat
18	B and D	High-preferred Attention and Academic Demands	C	Low-preferred Attention	Attention	Attention Type, Escape	High-preferred Attention and Academic Demands	Repeat
19	B and D	High-preferred Attention and Academic Demands	C	Low-preferred Attention	Attention	Attention Type, Escape	High-preferred Attention and Academic Demands	Avery tolerates demands when delivered by a preferred

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								RBT, Evaluate other potentially aversive stimuli
20	A	Escape	E	Attention, Losing a game		Attention, Escape	Attention, Losing a game	Repeat
21	A	Escape	E	Attention, Losing a game		Attention, Escape	Attention, Losing a game	Repeat
22	A	Escape	E	Attention, Losing a game		Attention, Escape	Attention, Losing a game	Avery can tolerate potentially aversive stimuli (i.e., chores, losing a game) when preferred attention is available